

Desire, Narcissism and Crisis in *Citizen Kane*

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[**Abstract:** This is a critical review of the cinema *Citizen Kane* (1941) directed by Orson Welles. The review seeks to understand the inner psychic drivers which lead human throughout the life, through the case of Charles Foster Kane and argues that the most primitive desire developed Kane's character in a narcissistic way which led him to fall in different types of crises. The review employs psychoanalysis as an approach to establish the argument.]

Key Words: desire, narcissism, crisis, ego, psyche, citizen kane

“Love, that's why he did everything.” _ Leyland

“But he never believed in anything except Charlie Kane.” _ Leyland

“He was a man who got everything he wanted and then lost it.” _ Thompson

A desire, a strong feeling to have something, which can lead one throughout the life, albeit he or she may not be satisfied meeting with the desired object because may be one himself or herself does not really know consciously what the ultimate desired object is. In some cases, this strong feeling may convert into narcissism which is somewhat self-centeredness, a lack of empathy, a need for admiration and this can lead one to different types of crises. *Citizen Kane* (1941) of Orson Welles is still a matter of debate to the film scholars with its confusing messages about the life and views of the great newspaper lord portrayed in the cinema.

From Previous Literatures:

There are two leading interpretations of the film *Citizen Kane* (1941) where one is enigma interpretation and another is Rosebud interpretation which Carroll¹ thinks incongruous. The enigma interpretation says, as he continues that ultimately, the nature of a person is a mystery as a person is different from different perspectives, on the other hand, the Rosebud interpretation refers Kane's personality with his searching of lost childhood or lost innocence, but it is never a mystery if the Rosebud explains everything or a mystery like Kane's life can never be understood with just the clue of Rosebud.

The personality of Charles Foster Kane is enigmatic. In real life, he is different to different people as Jarvie² contends, to his ex-wife, he is a person concerned with getting his own way; to his best friend, he is corrupted by egotism; to his manager, he is a creative and dynamic boss; to his guardian Thatcher, he is somehow dangerous; to his butler he is a man with feet of clay. Carrol³ thinks these views from different perspectives help to understand Kane, but not conflict with one another in factual matters as it does in *Rashomon* (1950).

News people are discussing about Kane's last word

The human mind is mysterious and Rosebud is somewhat flashback effect of memory which Welles tried to refer that everyone is affected by that particularly at the end of the life with the thought which Bradshaw⁴ thinks, childhood memories are better, simpler and real than adult memories.

Theoretical Framework

This study employs psychoanalysis to understand the life and views of Kane shown in the film where the Freudian model of the psyche and Lacanian theory of human psychic development are used mainly.

Kane and Desire: An Endless Well

Human is born into a condition of 'lack' which Lacan⁵ says 'the driver' which drives on one the whole life trying to fulfill this 'lack'. This notion of 'lack' is first understood in the mirror stage of human psychic development when a child feels that it is different from its mother with a self-identity which develops the 'ego' but at the same time it reminds the unconscious blissful feeling of the lost moment of the child when it was into the mother's womb.⁶ The relevant situation is found in the life of Charlie Kane. His mother sent him to live with Mr. Thatcher thinking of his proper education, though Charlie did not want to. Charlie's childhood was the most precious memory, thinking of which he haunts the whole life till death, which was symbolically portrayed with the snow globe, first shown at the very beginning of the cinema which was first found on the dressing table of Susan Alexander. Another reason Marry wanted Charlie living apart was to protect him from the ill-tempered father Jim. A close shot of little Charlie staring at his father with hatred explains it which is also can be explained by Freudian theory of 'Oedipus Complex' which Storey⁷ states that the mother becomes an object of the boy's desire since he takes father as a rival for the mother's love and affection that is why he wishes for the father's death.

Little Kane's expression to his father

Later in the interview what Jedediah says: "...his mother, I guess he always loved her". But after the childhood sequence, the father never comes for the second time in the whole cinema as in the memory of Charlie.

This eternal desire, love and affection of the mother made Charlie drive his whole life achieving many things as substitute, which is the job of 'ego' according to Storey⁸ as in the 'News on the March' sequence the narrator introduces Xanadu, the incomplete palace made by Charlie Kane which was called 'a collection of everything' with having statues, zoo, trees etc. and having ownership of radio stations, newspapers, apartment houses, mines, factories, forests, paper mills, but could not make him satisfied. This impossibility of fulfillment is experienced as a movement from signifier to signifier what we find from Leyland: "I don't suppose anybody ever had so many opinions", and Charlie's shift from collecting statue to diamond, first wife to second wife, newspaper editor to governor towards president what Storey⁹ states as "unable to fix upon a signified", Kane never finished a single thing he

started as Leyland remembers: "He never finished anything except my notice", which is proved by his unfinished palace in Xanadu, his incomplete political life, love life and so on.

From Love to Narcissism

Kane did many things because of love, not to give but to get as Leyland says in the interview: "Love, that's why he did everything... He loved Charlie Kane, of course, very dearly... But he never believed in anything except Charlie Kane" and again, after losing in the election: "Only you want love on your own terms".

Leyland, sharing his thoughts about Kane

Charlie Kane, the person who was split out from his most loved person, his mother Mary Kane, in his childhood, becomes nostalgic and grows up with an intense desire of love which makes him somehow narcissistic, concerned about himself only, thirsty of getting love from others in any way without thinking of them. This can be understood by Storey's¹⁰ explanation of Freud's final model of psyche. Freud perceives narcissism as a normal stage of child development but considers it as a disorder if it occurs after puberty. Narcissism can be said 'id in overdrive' where an individual is infatuated with himself, feels superior to others, obsesses over own achievements, believes himself too unique to be understood by others, lacks empathy for others and exploits others. One can find a narcissist to be competent and attractive at the beginning but over time, the narcissist will be revealed as arrogant and hostile.¹¹ All these characteristics feel harmony with Kane's. He is always infatuated with himself which is supported by his power. This is also portrayed with cinematic style showing Kane in low angle with high contrast of light and dark and dialogues.

What we see in the breakfast sequence that Kane is so much confident with his newspaper that he thinks people will think as he thinks about the president. Emily: "Really, Charles, people will think..." --- Kane: "What I tell them to think", and later his shout at Gettys, Kane: "There's only one person in the world to decide what I'll do and that's me..."

Kane becomes furious at Gettys

His feeling of being superior to others is found with another dialogue in his speech for election, supported by the low angle shot, Kane: "Now, however, I have something more than a hope Jim Gettys has something less than a chance"

He was obsessed with his own achievements too as he says to Thatcher, Kane: "...you don't realize you are talking to two people, as Charles Foster Kane who owns 82364 shares... on the other hand, I'm the publisher of The Inquirer". Though at that time, The Inquirer was not that much established as it became later. On the other hand, this is also established with the language of the Inquirer's Declaration of Principles' where uses 'I' two times though Jedediah reminds him about that. Here is to be noted that Kane claims himself of dual personality which is also clear with his works as the news on the March sequence describes him what Jarvie¹² says "to the right he was a communist; to the left a fascist; a man of the people who consorted with the rich and powerful; a foe of corruption who was himself corrupted by power; an amiable man with a stubborn and ruthless devotion to his own views".

No confusion he thought himself out of being understood by anyone though having his lack of empathy, the tendency of exploiting others which can be understood with the dialogues in the sequence of the picnic and when Susan tends to leave him. --- Susan: "You never really gave me anything that you care about. You just tried to buy me into giving you something" ---Kane: "Whatever I do, I do because I love you"---Susan: "You do not love me, you want me to love you".---Kane: "You can't do this to me"---Susan: "I see, it's you that this is being done to, it's not me at all"

This intense love to himself made things around him more critical which led his life into a complex sphere.

Towards Crisis: Led by Narcissism

So, what happened, Kane ran from one wish to another throughout his life but could never be satisfied what Lacan¹³ says unable to fix upon a specific one, because of his ultimate wish of getting back his lost childhood and inability to love others, ultimately made him fall in crises. As Leyland says: "All he wanted out of life was love. That's Charlie's story, how he lost it"

These narcissistic characteristics made him losing all the things he found. His best friend Jedediah, his chance of being governor and later president of United States, his wives, everything he lost one by one as his manager said to Thompson, "Mr. Kane was a man who lost almost everything he had"

The problems were first understood with the breakfast sequence where the distance between Kane and Emily was portrayed with their dialogues and finally established with newspapers where Kane reads

his Inquirer and Emily reads The Chronicle rejecting the Inquirer. Again, in the election campaign, Kane's upcoming crisis is shown with the high angle shot of Jim Gettys looking Kane giving the speech against him which later ends with the attempt to blackmail Kane and breaking of Kane's relationship with Emily providing the evidence of his extramarital relationship with Susan. In this sequence, in the low angle, three shot where at first, Kane and Gettys both were in a shadow and then Gettys comes ahead towards Emily revealing Kane's relationship with Susan revealing his face in light but Kane still remains in the dark as he is somehow guilty here to Emily. But he comes out of darkness when he decides not to cover his guilt as Gettys doing to save himself from the consequences of his crime.

As a result of refusing Gettys's proposal, his relationship with Susan comes out in front of people which makes himself a person to be hated and he loses the election. He loses both his first wife and his chance of being the governor but he marries Susan, which is another signifier according to Lacan¹⁴, but this is not stable also as Susan leaves him also when she finds out that all the things Kane does, trying to make Susan a singer, providing her everything that she needs but love, are just to satisfy himself as he says, "My reasons satisfy me, Susan. You seem unable to understand them".

His wish to make her an opera singer results in rupture with his best friend Jedediah as Kane violated the principle he declared, by publishing positive news about Susan's performance in opera though it was not true. The crisis between Susan and Kane is understood easily with the picnic sequence when they talk about their relationship which is emphasized with the song played in the picnic at night, "It can't be love, for there is no true love...lost in the end just the same". Here, the sound is an important symbol which refers to the inner feelings as there is heard screaming of a woman in the background when Kane slaps Susan, though no source is established.

And...Susan left Kane

Affirming Bernstein's notion about Kane, "the person who lost everything he had", with his personal life also lost his business properties at the time of the great depression (1929-1939) as stated in the news on the March sequence, Kane lived his last years alone in his unfinished palace, "...aloof, seldom visited, never photographed, an emperor of newsprint continued to direct his failing empire".

Charles Foster Kane, a person who in his entire life ran to get 'something' which was the most precious to him, made himself a self-centered man without thinking about others which led him to his distressed unhappy life till the end. The cinema revolves around to find out this 'something' which the journalist tries to find out about Kane's last uttered word 'Rosebud' but could not finally reveal, though the cinema reveals it to its audience showing Kane's childhood playing sled burning in the fire where the written word 'Rosebud' was being wiped.

Kane's childhood

It may refer that 'Rosebud' was 'something' which is only known to Kane himself and with his death, this is being abolished because no one will understand and no one needs to understand behind what he haunted the whole life. Though it may seem that 'Rosebud' may be a symbolic thing for Kane's lost childhood but again it is questioned with the shot of black smoke emitting from the chimney what Thomson compared with a missing piece of jigsaw puzzle and his notion of the word 'Rosebud', a single word which cannot explain a man's life. This is later emphasized with the last shot of the cinema 'NO TRESPASSING' written on signboard with which the cinema started, may be trying to say that Human psyche is the somewhat most mysterious thing in the world. One can try to analyze it with different approaches but in some cases, no one has the permission or ability to understand the real meaning of what a human mind wants, even the person himself.

Conclusion:

Citizen Kane (1941), the cinema is a realistic depiction of the relation between human psyche and real world. A never fulfilled desire of Charles Foster Kane drove him the whole life and made him doing different things in exchange which made him narcissistic and led to different crises throughout the life till the end.

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